

Religious Psychology Of Confession And Meditation

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Abstract: The article examines the psychology of religious confession and meditation, analysis of religious catharsis, psychological states, psychological methods, psychological processes.

Key words: psychology, religion, confession, meditation, catharsis, socio-oriented , religious “filling”.

INTRODUCTION.

The analysis of religious catharsis convinces us that certain psychological functional systems (dynamic stereotypes) acquire a specific social orientation, connecting with certain ideas and concepts. The religious “filling” of these systems fundamentally changes their role in the life of an individual, group and society. This conclusion can be supported by the analysis of psychological states and processes that arise in an individual during religious confession. First of all, it should be noted that people, regardless of their attitude to religion, have an objective psychological need for confession, i.e., a frank story about difficult and contradictory experiences, often intimate ones, about the complexities and vicissitudes of individual fate, about the mistakes and false steps they made in the past. This need is for sympathy, empathy, and consolation from the people around them. It should be noted that the very expression of “painful” issues helps a person to understand the problems that torment him. This is explained by the mechanism of verbalization of thoughts and feelings: what was initially not fully realized or was realized vaguely and indistinctly, during confession acquires clearer outlines, becomes more conscious. And this, as proven by numerous facts, brings a person a certain relief, consolation, helps him to make a decision in the future. Different people may have different motivations for the need for confession, acquire different content. For some, this

is one of the ways to subject their life, their past to the judgment of conscience, i.e. judgment from a moral standpoint. For others, ideological searches, the desire to find the meaning of life come to the fore. There are also those for whom the desire for moral self-improvement is organically combined with the search for firm ideological ones. A striking example of people of the latter type is L. N. Tolstoy. No less varied are the forms in which the psychological need for confession is realized. It has long been noted in fiction that people often have an at first glance inexplicable desire to share with strangers, random fellow travelers, etc. Why do people sometimes trust strangers or little-known people more than their loved ones? Several factors are at work here. It is important that in this case the anonymous listener will not be able to abuse the experiences entrusted to him and not intended for wide discussion. Consequently, the “secret of confession” is necessary, which in this case is ensured by the anonymity of the listener. It also happens that confession is intended for the closest friend or family member, to whom this person has confidence. It is interesting that ethnographers have recorded the presence of the act of confession among a number of peoples who were at the stage of tribal relations. Confession acquired a magical significance there: it was required when a misfortune occurred in the life of a tribe, which, according to the beliefs of the members of this tribe, was caused by the violation of a taboo (i.e.

prohibitions that have a religious and magical significance) by one of the tribesmen. In this case, there is only one way of “purification” and preventing further troubles and misfortunes: all members of the tribe must confess and the one who violated the taboo is obliged to openly admit it, “... To restore the purity of a social group, one preliminary condition is necessary. It is necessary for the guilty one, i.e. the one who has become infected with filth, to admit his guilt. Confession is necessary. Until then, the harmful consequences continue to follow one after another.

And then Levy-Bruhl gives many examples confirming precisely this “magical” interpretation of confession by many tribes and peoples. Religious organizations very skillfully used the psychological need for confession. The Catholic and Orthodox churches elevated it to the rank of a special “sacrament”, i.e. the most important rite, through which the believer allegedly receives special “divine grace”. “It must be recognized that confession is a powerful means of influence and control in the hands of the church. Individual, based on mutual trust, communication between a priest and a parishioner is a great invention of the clergy.” The inclusion of certain psychological stereotypes in the system of religious doctrine and cult changes their social orientation. In the process of religious confession, the negative experiences accumulated by the confessor are “removed”. This psychological process is painted entirely in religious tones: the believer is convinced that his confession and repentance will reach God through the church, that forgiveness of sins will also ultimately be granted by God. The Church skillfully used the need for the “secret of confession” by making it (formally) a norm obligatory for priests. It took into account the need of people for moral correction and improvement, giving it religious content: the priest as a representative of God forgives any sins, even the most serious ones, thereby emphasizing the

boundless mercy of God. Religious confession took an important place in the system of means and methods that provide religious consolation. Another functional psychological system that plays an important role in many religions and cults as an effective means of psychological consolation and overcoming negative experiences is meditation. “Philosophical Encyclopedic Dictionary” defines meditation (from Latin Meditation - reflection) as a mental activity of the individual, the purpose of which is to achieve a state of “deep concentration. In the psychological aspect, meditation involves the elimination of extreme emotional manifestations and a significant decrease in reactivity.

The somatic state of the meditator is characterized by relaxation, and his mental state is elation and some detachment (from external objects and individual internal experiences)”. As is clear from this characteristic, meditation in itself is not necessarily connected with religion. For example, one can imagine a scientist who uses meditation to fully concentrate on some scientific problem. Meditation can also be included in the system of psychotherapeutic and even pedagogical activity. However, historically it turned out that the methods and techniques of meditation were developed in detail in a number of religions, primarily Eastern ones (in Hinduism, Buddhism, etc.)

Meditation, becoming an important form of cult actions and being included in the system of religious beliefs, acquires important socio-psychological features. If meditation is a special mental state of the individual, which contributes to the formation of deep concentration, then the question of what the person is focused on is of no small importance: what ideas and images are in the center of his attention, are realized and experienced by him. The literature devoted to Eastern religions emphasizes the importance of meditation as a way of influencing the psyche of believers. Characterizing the role of meditation in the system

of Chinese Chan (deen) Buddhism, N.V. Abaev and E.B. Porshneva write "... a very important and often decisive role in the process of forming the basic socio-psychological attitudes and the entire value-orientation structure among members of these sects was played by various methods of meditation borrowed from the Chan practice of psychotraining and mental self-regulation: both individual and collective (or joint with a teacher-mentor), both outwardly passive and active-dynamic.

In accordance with the fundamental principles of the religious-philosophical ethical and psychological teachings of Chan Buddhism, these methods were intended to displace the usual logical and verbal structures from the consciousness of the adept and to evoke in him non-verbal experiences of intuitive enlightenment or illumination." All this once again confirms the correctness of the conclusion that psychological functional systems (catharsis, confession, meditation) providing religious consolation can function outside of religious ideological content; they should not be identified with religious beliefs and ideas.

However, in the system of religious worship they are connected with the corresponding beliefs and this is what determines the nature of their impact on the individual and society. The consolation that religion gives is an illusory consolation, achieved by temporarily deviating from reality. Religion consoles, but does not ease the living conditions of people. And this is precisely why the need arises. In liberating people from religious consolation "The abolition of religion as the illusory happiness of the people is the demand for its real happiness.

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